

Study of axial Xenon Oscillations of a thermal reactor using a 1D diffusion model in one group of energy with an adapted Doppler effect.

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a one-dimensional, one-group diffusion model developed to investigate axial xenon oscillations in thermal reactors. The proposed model extends the work of Mercier et al. 2020 by reformulating the Doppler feedback to provide what we believe is a more physically consistent response especially under significant fuel temperature changes. We also suggest a way to model moderator temperature feedback effects. While numerous three-dimensional, multi-group models exist for analyzing xenon oscillations with higher accuracy, they are often computationally demanding and complex to implement. In contrast, the present model offers a much faster, more accessible, and flexible framework, making it well suited for parametric studies, sensitivity analyses, and to provide easy safety criteria for load-following for instance. Model predictions are consistent with established results, confirming that larger migration areas and stronger feedback effects tend to attenuate axial xenon oscillations. Overall, this simplified yet physically grounded model provides valuable insights into the dynamic behavior of xenon transients in thermal reactors and serves as an efficient computational tool that could be used for pedagogical purposes to explore feedback mechanisms and control strategies, even for load-following safety checks given that control rods for load-following can also be implemented in the model.

Keywords: Xenon, Diffusion, PWR, Feedback, Control

1. INTRODUCTION

Xenon oscillations are a well-known phenomenon in thermal reactors reported as early as 1955 in Savannah River [1]. It is of importance given that $^{135}_{54}\text{Xe}$ is the fission product with the highest absorption cross section, therefore, xenon oscillations can lead to power distribution changes that may challenge some safety or operational limits of the reactor. This can lead to an automatic shutdown in a PWR if the oscillations are not properly controlled [2]. During load-following operations, movement of control rods create perturbations in the neutron flux that can potentially lead to Xenon oscillations (see, for instance [3]). It might therefore be useful to have a fast yet accurate model to predict the amplitude of these oscillations in order to define safe load-following strategies given that there are many possible dispatch scenarios (in that regard, see, for instance, [4]).

The present work aims to develop such a model originally inspired by the 1D and 1 group model of [5]. Although 3D oscillation modes of Xenon exist ([6], [2]), the main modes of oscillation are axial ([2], [3], [4]), hence the 1D approximation. This phenomenon can be explained by smaller radial dimensions than axial dimensions of the core and by the fact that control rod perturbations are rather radially symmetrical and axially [2]. Regarding the one-group approximation, [5] shows that a 1 group model provides very similar results to a 2 group model for xenon oscillations. The present work models the Doppler feedback effect differently from [5], and suggests ways to incorporate the moderator temperature feedback and control rods into the model.

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2. OUR MODIFIED 1-GROUP DIFFUSION MODEL

In this section, we recall the basic building blocks of the model, already present in [5], before introducing our modification for the Doppler feedback effect.

The 1D stationary neutron diffusion equation can be written as follows for a homogeneous reactor of height H :

$$-M^2\Phi''(z) + \Phi(z) = k_\infty\Phi(z), \quad 0 < z < H, \quad (1)$$

where M^2 is the migration area, H is the height of the core, and Φ is taken as the neutron flux here. In our case, we first considered Dirichlet boundary conditions $\Phi(0) = \Phi(H) = 0$ to compare our work to [5]. The solution to this equation is defined up to a multiplicative constant that can be determined by fixing the total power of the reactor. We remind the reader that the migration area is defined as follows.

$$M^2 := L^2 + \tau_{th}, \quad L^2 := \frac{D}{\Sigma_a}, \quad \tau_{th} = \int_{E_{th}}^{\infty} \frac{D(E)}{\zeta(E)\Sigma_s(E)E} dE \quad (2)$$

where D is the diffusion coefficient, Σ_a the macroscopic absorption cross section, ζ the average gain of lethargy, and Σ_s the macroscopic scattering cross section.

Finally, we also remind the reader that k_∞ is the infinite multiplication factor defined as:

$$k_\infty = \frac{\nu\Sigma_f}{\Sigma_a}, \quad (3)$$

where ν is the average number of neutrons emitted per fission and Σ_f is the macroscopic fission cross section. In this 1-group model, Φ is assumed to represent the thermal flux.

2.1. Xenon and Iodine evolution equations

To model the evolution of Xenon concentration, we use the following coupled equations for $^{135}_{53}I$ and $^{135}_{54}Xe$:

$$\frac{\partial Y}{\partial t} = \gamma\Sigma_f\Phi - \lambda Y, \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{\partial X}{\partial t} = \gamma'\Sigma_f\Phi + \lambda Y - (\sigma\Phi + \mu)X, \quad (5)$$

where Y is the concentration of iodine, X is the concentration of Xenon, γ and γ' are the fission yields of Iodine and Xenon, respectively, λ is the decay constant of $^{135}_{53}I$, σ is the microscopic absorption cross section of $^{135}_{54}Xe$ and μ is the decay constant of $^{135}_{54}Xe$.

In the following, we use a common simplification to neglect the generation of Xenon that directly results from fission (term $\gamma'\Sigma_f\Phi$ in Equation (5)) since $\gamma' \ll \gamma$.

Denote by ω the volumetric share of fuel within the core. In a PWR, $\omega \approx \frac{1}{3}$. Then, if X is the concentration of Xenon within the fuel, the macroscopic absorption cross section of Xenon within a homogenized core can be expressed as ωX . Therefore, when Xenon is introduced into the core, the diffusion Equation (1) becomes:

$$-M^2\Phi'' + (1 + \alpha X)\Phi = k_{\infty,0}\Phi, \quad (6)$$

where according to [5] $\alpha = \frac{\sigma\omega}{\Sigma_a}$ and $k_{\infty,0}$ is the infinite multiplication factor without Xenon. In fact, we believe that α should be redefined as $\alpha = \frac{f_d\sigma\omega}{\Sigma_a}$ where $f_d = \frac{\Phi_{fuel}}{\Phi_{cell}}$ is the thermal disadvantage factor. Indeed, these weighting by the flux ensures that reaction rates are conserved, but we did not use the latter expression, in order to be able to compare our results with [5]. All variables in the problem depend on the axial position z and on time t .

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Height of the core	H	400cm
Macroscopic fission cross section	Σ_f	0.246 cm^{-1}
Macroscopic absorption cross section	Σ_a	0.115 cm^{-1}
Microscopic absorption cross section of $^{135}_{54}\text{Xe}$	σ	$2 \times 10^6 \text{ barn}$
Decay constant of $^{135}_{53}\text{I}$	λ	$2.92 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$
Decay constant of $^{135}_{54}\text{Xe}$	μ	$2.12 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$
Fission yield of $^{135}_{53}\text{I}$	γ	0.064
Volumic share of fuel in core	ω	1/3

Table I. Typical parameters used in the model

2.2. Rescaling the equations

To simplify the problem and for numerical purposes, we also rescale the equations. We define the following dimensionless variables:

$$\Phi(z, t) = \Phi^* \phi(z, t), \quad X(z, t) = X^* x(z, t), \quad Y(z, t) = Y^* y(z, t), \quad t = \frac{\tau}{\lambda}, \quad a = \frac{\mu}{\lambda}, \quad (7)$$

where $\Phi^* = \frac{\lambda}{\sigma}$ and $X^* = Y^* = \frac{\gamma \Sigma_f}{\sigma}$. Using these new variables, the equations become:

$$\frac{dy}{d\tau} = \phi - y, \quad \frac{dx}{d\tau} = y - (\phi + a)x, \quad -M^2 \phi'' + (1 + \alpha^* x)\phi = k_{\infty,0} \phi. \quad (8)$$

where $\alpha^* = \alpha X^* = \omega \frac{\gamma \Sigma_f}{\Sigma_a}$.

We will use typical values for the different parameters as suggested by [5] and summarized in Table I.

2.3. Taking into account the Doppler feedback effect

In [5], the Doppler feedback effect is modeled by the following non-linear adjustment of the diffusion equation:

$$-M^2 \phi'' + (1 + \alpha^* x)\phi = k_{\infty,0}(1 - \beta\phi)\phi, \quad (9)$$

The modeling of the Doppler feedback effect is inspired by [7], where a negative macroscopic cross section proportional to the neutron flux is added to the initial absorption cross section. This approach can be interpreted as a first-order Taylor expansion of the Doppler impact on the quantity $\nu \Sigma_f - \Sigma_a$ around the zero-flux state. Indeed, Doppler broadening affects both Σ_a and Σ_f through resonance broadening and depends on the fuel temperature, which can reasonably be assumed to vary linearly with the neutron flux at first order. However, this linear approximation may lead to non-physical results when the flux departs significantly from zero, as its validity then becomes questionable. To address this limitation, we propose an alternative way of incorporating the Doppler effect into the model.

The Doppler reactivity coefficient α_{dop} can be defined as follows [8]:

$$\alpha_{dop} = \frac{1}{p} \frac{\partial p}{\partial T_f}, \quad (10)$$

where p is the resonance escape probability in Fermi's four factor formula [9] and T_f is the fuel temperature. Therefore, using the four factor formula, the following differential equation is provided for the infinite multiplication factor:

$$\frac{\partial k_\infty}{\partial T_f} = \alpha_{dop} k_\infty. \quad (11)$$

which can be solved to give:

$$k_\infty(T_f) = k_\infty(T_{f,0}) \exp \left(\int_{T_{f,0}}^{T_f} \alpha_{dop}(s) ds \right), \quad (12)$$

where $T_{f,0}$ is the reference fuel temperature at which $k_\infty = k_{\infty,0}$.

If one linearizes this expression around $T_{f,0} = T_f(\phi = 0)$ and then linearizes the fuel temperature around $\phi = 0$, one recovers the model of [5]. However, we choose to keep the exponential form of Equation (12) to ensure a more physically consistent behavior of the Doppler effect at higher flux values. To use this expression, we need to express the Doppler coefficient as a function of the fuel temperature. We use the following empirical law mentioned in [10] and given with explicit values for a PWR in [2]:

$$\alpha_{dop}(T_f) \approx \alpha_{dop}(573.15K) \sqrt{\frac{573.15}{T_f}} \quad (13)$$

with $\alpha_{dop}(573.15K) \approx -3.25 pcm/K$ and T_f in Kelvin.

3. RESOLUTION OF THE MODIFIED DIFFUSION EQUATION

3.1. Temporal Resolution: semi-implicit scheme

Similarly to [5] we use a semi-implicit scheme to solve the equation in time. Let us note that we do not model delayed neutrons explicitly because the time step used is large compared to characteristic emission times of delayed neutrons, as is common in such problems (e.g., [2],[5], [6]). Denote the time step δ such that $\tau_n = n\delta$. At each time step, we solve the following system:

$$y^n - \delta(\phi^n - y^n) = y^{n-1}, \quad (14)$$

$$x^n - \delta(y^n - (\phi^n + a)x^n) = x^{n-1}, \quad (15)$$

And finally we solve the modified diffusion equation:

$$-M^2 \phi^{n''} + (1 + \alpha^* x^n) \phi^n = k_{\infty,0} \exp \left(\int_{T_{f,0}}^{T_f(\phi^{n-1})} \alpha_{dop}(s) ds \right) \phi^n \quad (16)$$

Looking for the eigenvectors associated with the smallest eigenvalue of the following operator:

$$\mathcal{L}(\phi) = -M^2 \phi'' + \left(\exp \left(- \int_{T_{f,0}}^{T_f(\phi^{n-1})} \alpha_{dop}(s) ds \right) + \alpha^* x \right) \phi \quad (17)$$

Here, we simplified the operator by removing the negligible cross terms given that $-\int_{T_{f,0}}^{T_f(\phi^{n-1})} \alpha_{dop}(s) ds \ll 1$.

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Fuel pin radius	r_f	0.41 cm
Clad inner radius	r_i	0.418 cm
Clad outer radius	r_c	0.475 cm
Convective heat transfer coefficient in the gap	h	0.34 W/cm ² .K

Table II. Parameters used to compute the fuel temperature

3.2. Spatial Resolution

To discretize the spatial domain, we use a uniform grid with points $N + 2$ and a spatial step $\Delta z = \frac{H}{N+1}$. The second derivative in the diffusion equation is approximated by using central finite differences:

$$\phi''(z_i) \approx \frac{\phi(z_{i+1}) - 2\phi(z_i) + \phi(z_{i-1}))}{\Delta z^2}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N \quad (18)$$

where $z_i = i\Delta z$. The boundary conditions $\phi(0) = \phi(H) = 0$ are applied at the first and last points of the grid by setting the first and last rows of the operator matrix \mathcal{L} to zero.

In order to compute the fuel temperature $T_f(\phi)$ we solve the heat equation within each axial slice, assuming that the heat is generated proportionally to the neutron flux in the fuel pin, and we use the Rowlands correlation for the effective fuel temperature [11]. The parameters used are summarized in Table II.

The effective fuel temperature is defined as:

$$T_{eff} = \frac{4}{9}T_{f,int} + \frac{5}{9}T_{f,ext}, \quad (19)$$

where $T_{f,int}$ is the temperature at the center of the fuel and $T_{f,ext}$ is the temperature at the outer surface of the fuel pellet.

We compute $T_{f,int}$ as the value of T_f that satisfies

$$\int_{T_{f,ext}}^{T_f} \lambda_{\text{UO}_2}(T) dT = \frac{q r_f^2}{4}. \quad (20)$$

Here, q is the heat generation rate in the fuel (defined as $q = \Sigma_f \Phi \kappa_f$, where κ_f is the energy released per fission taken to be roughly 200 MeV), which is proportional to the local neutron flux ϕ , and $\lambda_{\text{UO}_2}(T)$ is the thermal conductivity of UO_2 as a function of temperature T . We use a Lucuta empirical relation for $\lambda_{\text{UO}_2}(T)$ [12]. We define $T_{f,ext}$ as follows

$$T_{f,ext} = T_{clad,in} + \frac{q r_c}{2h}, \quad (21)$$

where $T_{clad,in}$ is the inner surface temperature of the cladding, which is the solution to the following equation:

$$\int_{T_{mod}}^{T_{clad,in}} \lambda_{clad}(T) dT = \frac{q r_f^2 \ln(r_c/r_i)}{2} \quad (22)$$

with T_{mod} the moderator temperature and $\lambda_{clad}(T)$ the thermal conductivity of the cladding material, for which we use an empirical relation obtained from internal communication within CEA. Finally, it is assumed that the moderator temperature will vary according to a temperature program given in [2] that fixes the objective input and outlet temperatures of the moderator. The profile between these two points is calculated using the heat generated in the fuel within each axial slice and then rescaled to match the objective outlet temperature.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To compare our model, we reproduce some of the results presented in [5] with the parameters given in Table I. We first compute a steady state solution by setting the time derivatives in equations Equation (14) and Equation (15) to zero and solving the resulting equations coupled with the diffusion Equation (16). We then perturb the system by decreasing the Xenon concentration by 10% in the lower half of the core and increasing it by 10% in the upper half of the core. We then let the system evolve in time using the semi-implicit scheme described earlier. The flux is normalized at each time step to keep the total power constant (here the average value of ϕ is set to 3). We then compute the power axial offset defined as:

$$AO(t) = \frac{\int_{H/2}^H \phi(z, t) dz - \int_0^{H/2} \phi(z, t) dz}{\int_0^H \phi(z, t) dz} \quad (23)$$

The result depicted in Figure 1 shows the evolution of the axial offset oscillations of the power caused by

Figure 1. Power axial offset at different times after a perturbation of the steady state. Subfigure (a) corresponds to oscillations obtained with Σ_f defined as in Table I, whereas subfigure (b) increases this Σ_f value by 18% and subfigure (c) increases it by 26%. The damping of the oscillations becomes more pronounced as Σ_f increases, due to the higher effective fuel temperature resulting from the same flux normalization.

the Xenon oscillation at different times after the perturbation. We observe that these oscillations slightly dampen over time, in a manner similar to what is observed in [5] with the same test case, although the damping seems slightly less pronounced with our model. The period of the oscillations and their initial amplitude is also very similar to what is reported in [5]. However, we notice that, in contrast to [5], the axial offset of the power is initially slightly negative and converges to this slightly negative value over time, while in [5] the axial offset at equilibrium is zero. This difference is explained by the fact that our model of the Doppler effect explicitly depends on the fuel temperature, which itself depends on the moderator temperature. The increase of the moderator temperature with height in our model leads to a stronger Doppler feedback effect in the upper part of the core, which in turn leads to a slightly negative axial offset at equilibrium. Therefore, our model seems to capture more physics. Regarding the influence of the different parameters that appear in the model, we recover the same trends as in [5], namely that increasing the migration area M^2 or increasing the strength of the Doppler feedback effect (by increasing $|\alpha_{dop}|$ or the power generation, as shown in Figure 1) leads to a decrease in the amplitude of the Xenon oscillations. In contrast, increasing the height of the core H leads to an increase in the amplitude of the oscillations (in that regard the meaningful parameter is actually $\frac{H}{M}$ according to [5]). These results are not shown here for the sake of brevity, but are available upon request.

5. FURTHER REFINEMENT OF THE MODEL

The previous equations aimed to introduce an alternative to [5] to model the impact of the Doppler effect on Xenon oscillations. We also explored further refinement of our xenon oscillation model not considered in [5]: the moderator temperature feedback effect and the modeling of control rods.

Concerning the modeling of the temperature feedback effect defined as (see, for instance [8]):

$$CTM(T_m) := \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial T_m} \quad (24)$$

we take advantage of the fact that some formulae are given in [2] just like we had a formula for the Doppler effect in Equation (13). This allows us to compute the solution of Equation (24):

$$k_\infty(T_m) = \frac{k_\infty(T_{m,0})}{1 - \int_{T_{m,0}}^{T_m} CTM(s) ds} \quad (25)$$

However, we must be careful before using Equation (25) to account for the moderator effect: one should not only apply the multiplicative factor of the feedback on k_∞ just like we did in Equation (16) with the Doppler feedback factor. Indeed, in this case, we noticed with an independent lattice calculation on a PWR assembly that one factor on the left hand-side of Equation (16) varies significantly with the moderator temperature : M^2 . Therefore, we first have to apply a correction to M^2 when T_m varies. We did that in the following way:

$$M^2(T_m) = M^2(T_{m,0}) \times (1 - K \times \int_{T_{m,0}}^{T_m} CTM(s) ds) \quad (26)$$

where K was estimated using results from lattice calculation to fit Equation (26). Then, once again neglecting cross-terms, the eigenvalues to determine become those of the following operator:

$$\mathcal{L}(\phi) = -M^2 \times \left(1 - K \times \int_{T_{m,0}}^{T_m} CTM(s) ds\right) \phi'' + \left(\exp\left(-\int_{T_{f,0}}^{T_f} \alpha_{dop}(s) ds\right) + \alpha^* x - \int_{T_{m,0}}^{T_m} CTM(s) ds\right) \phi \quad (27)$$

Concerning the modeling of the control rods, we dilute them within the cells to obtain the average concentrations of control rod material per cell R , and we add a term similar to the term xenon to the diffusion equation Equation (1):

$$\alpha^* x \rightarrow \alpha^* x + \alpha_{rod}^* r \quad (28)$$

where $\alpha_{rod}^* = \alpha_{rod} \times R^*$, with $\alpha_{rod} = \frac{f_d \omega \sigma_{rod}}{\Sigma_a}$ and $R = R^* \times r = X^* \times r$.

Although some first results on rod worth, xenon oscillation period and attenuation seem to indicate that these refinements to our model behave correctly against results displayed in [2], we are still trying to validate or potentially correct them against a more precise 3D core calculation where all the parameters of the core are precisely known.

6. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we presented a modified 1D, 1-group diffusion model to study axial Xenon oscillations in thermal reactors. The main novelty of our approach lies in modeling the Doppler feedback effect, which

we reformulated to ensure a more physically consistent response under significant fuel temperature changes. Our results are consistent with established findings, confirming that larger migration areas and stronger feedback effects tend to attenuate axial xenon oscillations. We also introduced ways to model moderator temperature feedback effects and control rods. The logical next step for this work would be to validate our model against experimental data from a real reactor or against more complex multi-group, 3D simulations to further assess its accuracy and reliability. However, this validation step requires some additional work to adapt the model to a specific reactor geometry and material properties, especially given phenomena such as those pointed out in [13] regarding the influence of reflectors that seem to result in a higher effective reactor height. It should be noted that the model is very sensitive to some parameter choices, as evidenced in Figure 1.

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